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**THE INFLUENCE OF GAMIFICATION ON VOCABULARY ACQUISITION: A
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF WORDWALL AND BAAMBOOZLE**

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***Abstract:** gamification has become an increasingly popular approach in English language teaching, particularly for enhancing learners’ motivation and vocabulary development. The aim of the study described in the article is to compare the impact of the platforms Wordwall and Baamboozle on vocabulary acquisition among 10th grade English language learners. A quasi-experimental design was employed involving two groups of 15 students with English proficiency levels ranging from A2 to B1. One group engaged in vocabulary learning activities through Baamboozle, while the other used Wordwall. The findings indicated that both platforms contributed positively to vocabulary development. However, students using Wordwall demonstrated greater gains in vocabulary acquisition compared to those using Baamboozle. Survey results revealed that learners perceived Wordwall as a more convenient and effective tool for individual practice and revision, whereas Baamboozle was valued for promoting enjoyment, collaboration, and classroom interaction.*

***Keywords:** gamification, vocabulary acquisition, Wordwall, Baamboozle, ELT*

Vocabulary plays a fundamental role in modern foreign education methodology, as it serves as the cornerstone of effective communication. Xerri (2024) believes that knowledge of vocabulary has a beneficial impact on various competencies related to knowledge of the language: reading, listening, writing, and speaking, thus, it affects both productive and receptive skills and is an influential parameter in language acquisition [1]. Consistent with Danilina and Shabunina (2020), vocabulary acquisition constitutes a fundamental component of mastering the English language, as it enhances the communication process and fosters learners’ self-confidence [2]. Although vocabulary acquisition is an essential aspect of language learning, learners often face motivational difficulties that can hinder their ability to remember and use newly learned words. To address this problem, educators have adopted gamification strategies. Following Vathanalaotha (2022), gamification in the context of English Language Teaching (ELT) is a dynamic pedagogical strategy that involves integrating game elements, mechanics, and principles into the traditional language learning process [3]. Park and Kim (2021) argue that gamification in vocabulary acquisition significantly increases learners' engagement by making the learning process more organized and active [4]. Panmei and Waluyo (2023) found that gamification in vocabulary learning increases enthusiasm for aligning various learning methods that stimulate auditory, visual, verbal, and other senses [5]. In compliance with Nikmah (2020), gamification in vocabulary learning encourages learners to participate in a proactive learning environment and actively extend their vocabulary knowledge by reinforcing it into active vocabulary through comprehensive application [6]. This study is devoted to a comparative analysis of the impact of Wordwall and Baamboozle platforms for gamification of vocabulary acquisition. Although gamification through these platforms has been broadly used to enhance the process of learning lexical material, empirical data are deficient in comparing the impact of Wordwall and Baamboozle on foreign vocabulary acquisition. Analysis of the impact of these platforms exists, but only in isolation from each other. For example, a study by Walidaina (2024) on the effectiveness of Baamboozle found significant improvements in vocabulary learning among seventh-graders. Another study by Valladares (2024) assessed the impact of Wordwall on vocabulary learning among primary school learners and found positive results.

Wordwall and Baamboozle are popular gamified learning platforms widely used in language education. Wordwall provides a range of interactive activities, including quizzes, matching exercises, crossword puzzles, and guessing games, which support both individual and classroom learning. In contrast, Baamboozle is primarily designed for team-based games and promotes collaboration, communication, and learner engagement through competitive group activities. Due to their different game mechanics and modes of interaction, these platforms offer distinct opportunities for vocabulary learning and learner motivation.

The study participants were 10th grade learners of School No. 16 in Kokshetau. Two full groups (n=15 each) took part in the study. All learners had pre-intermediate to intermediate English proficiency (A2–B1) according to the national curriculum. They studied English as a foreign language. Group 1 used Baamboozle during lessons, while Group 2 used Wordwall.

Vocabulary knowledge was assessed using three instruments: a pre-test, formative tests, and a post-test. The vocabulary tests consisted of four task types: matching words with their definitions, completing sentences with appropriate vocabulary items, identifying synonyms or antonyms, and using target words in context. These tasks were designed to assess different dimensions of vocabulary acquisition, including recognition, comprehension, and productive use. These tests were designed to assess vocabulary retention and help monitor learning progress in real time. The vocabulary items used in the pre-, formative, and post-tests were drawn from the thematic units taught during the study period, covering topics such as Space, Science Films, and NASA. Each test included 10-15 target vocabulary items, carefully selected to reflect key lexical items from the textbook. All tests were reviewed by two experienced English teachers to ensure level consistency and relevance to the curriculum. All tested vocabulary items were taken from the student book “Action for Kazakhstan” by Jenny Dooley, published by Express Publishing [7].

A comparison between the Baamboozle and Wordwall groups demonstrates significant differences in vocabulary acquisition outcomes. Both groups showed improvement between pre-test and post-test, but the Wordwall group exhibited a greater gain. The results of the pretest and posttest showed the following values: Baamboozle: Average pre-test score = 4.3/10 (43 %), post-test score = 7.1/10 (71 %), Wordwall: Average pre-test score = 4.07/10 (40.7%), post-test score = 7.7/10 (77 %). The results showed an average increase for Baamboozle of +3.00 points, while for Wordwall, +3.7 points (Figure 1 and Figure 2).

Figure 1: Comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores for Baamboozle Group

Figure 2: Comparison of Pre-Test and Post-Test Scores for Wordwall Group

The findings indicate that both Baamboozle and Wordwall contributed positively to learners' vocabulary development. However, the Wordwall group demonstrated a greater improvement in post-test performance, suggesting that the platform may be more effective for vocabulary acquisition and retention. These results support the use of gamified learning tools in English language instruction for school learners and suggest that both platforms may offer particular advantages for enhancing vocabulary acquisition, retention, and independent practice among secondary school students.

In addition, both groups completed a short survey after the experiment. It included Likert scales and open-ended questions to assess learners' engagement and effectiveness of the platforms. The survey was specifically designed for each group and consisted of two sections: learners' engagement and learning effectiveness. The Wordwall group answered the following open-ended questions:

- “How much did you enjoy the Wordwall activity?”
- “Did the face-to-face format increase your confidence?”
- “Did the game encourage you to remember new words?”

They also rated their agreement with the following statements with responses ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

- “The variety of activities helped me remember new vocabulary more effectively”
- “The platform was easy to navigate and use independently”
- “I would like to use this platform for learning vocabulary in future English lessons”
- “The platform made learning new vocabulary more interesting than traditional classroom exercises”

Similarly, the Baamboozle group answered the questions:

- “Did the team format increase your motivation?”
- “Did the competition between teams help you remember vocabulary better?”

The learners also evaluated the following statements from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree):

- “I would like to use this platform for learning vocabulary in future English lessons”
- “The game format helped me stay focused throughout the activity”
- “Working with my teammates helped me learn new vocabulary more effectively”
- “Team discussions encouraged me to use English more actively during the activity”
- “The platform made learning new vocabulary more interesting than traditional classroom exercises”

The survey results demonstrated a positive perception of both platforms. In the Wordwall group ($n = 15$), 87% of learners reported that they enjoyed the activities and found them engaging. Approximately 80% agreed that the variety of activities helped them remember new vocabulary more effectively, while 93% indicated that the platform was easy to navigate and use independently. Furthermore, 87% expressed a willingness to use Wordwall in future English lessons, and 80% believed that it made vocabulary learning more interesting than traditional classroom exercises.

The Baamboozle group also reported positive experiences. About 93% of learners stated that the team format increased their motivation, and 87% agreed that competition between teams helped them retain vocabulary more effectively. In addition, 80% reported that working with teammates supported vocabulary learning, while 87% noted that team discussions encouraged them to use English more actively during the activity. Moreover, 80% of participants indicated that the game format helped them stay focused, and 87% agreed that Baamboozle made vocabulary learning more engaging than traditional methods.

Overall, the survey findings suggest that both platforms had a positive impact on learners' motivation, engagement, and vocabulary learning. However, Wordwall was perceived as particularly effective for independent practice and vocabulary reinforcement, whereas Baamboozle was valued for promoting collaboration, communication, and active classroom participation.

The results of the study are important for foreign language teachers. Teachers can confidently apply gamification elements to increase motivation and efficiency in vocabulary acquisition. In particular, Wordwall is well-suited for structured review and reinforcement, especially when preparing for tests or exams. At the same time, Baamboozle is better used to stimulate teamwork, interactive lessons, and game-based repetitions aimed at increasing interest and engagement. The platform should match the specific goal of the lesson.

Teachers are encouraged to combine both platforms depending on the goals of the lesson. For example, use Wordwall for individual practice and Baamboozle for group reinforcement and game quizzes. This approach allows for different learning styles and maintains a balance between motivation and academic progress.

This study had several limitations. First, the small sample size (two groups of 15 people) reduces the generalizability of the results. A larger and more diverse sample would provide more reliable evidence and increase the validity of the results. Second, the duration of the experiment was short, which does not allow for an assessment of long-term memory. Also, random sampling was not used, as the groups were formed in advance. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of gamification in vocabulary learning and demonstrates the positive impact of digital educational tools on student engagement and motivation.

Future studies should be conducted on different age groups, with a larger number of participants. Furthermore, future investigations could explore how gamification influences other language skills, including speaking, writing, reading, and listening. Researchers may also compare different gamification platforms and game elements to determine which features contribute most effectively to language learning outcomes and learner motivation.

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